

Chemical Tempering of Flexible Glasses

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ABSTRACT

Since last decade, smartphones have revolutionised human life; however, this market, which was booming a couple of years ago, has driven into stagnation due to lacking materials able to cope with the demand for better, smaller and stretchable devices. This bottleneck can be overcome by using chemically tempered glasses that are strong and flexible despite being brittle.

This presentation explores the chemical tempering of thin silicate glasses; influences of being subjected to Na-K ion exchange and typical parameters, such as temperature and time, on the generation of compressive residual stress and mechanical properties have been investigated.

Keywords: Chemical tempering, Silicate Glass, Mechanical properties.

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